

FROM THE HISTORY OF CONSTITUTIONS AND SUFFRAGE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. The article highlights the history of the constitutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan before the country gained independence. It focuses on the sections of constitutions related to elections, analyzes the political aspects of the present system and period, as well as issues related to the electoral process. In addition, the issues related to the information on class relations contained in the constitutions are highlighted.

Keywords: constitution, Soviet power, kurultai, Council of people's nazirs, elections, disenfranchisement, voting, deprived.

Each child of the country has a careful study of all the realities associated with his past from the riddles of the history of his homeland. Therefore, the deep and objective coverage of the history of the roads that have been conquered until the time of our people's experiences, the fate of our compatriots and the arrival of such bright ones as today is our main duty to our people.

With the information we will bring below, we will try to cover the history of the constitutions that have been practiced to this day in our independent homeland with our main focus on the sections related to the electoral system, their political aspects in the existing system and periods.

The Constitution is the Basic Law of the state, which determines the structure of the state, the system of government and management agencies, their competence and the procedure for formation, the electoral system, the rights and freedoms of citizens, as well as the judicial system. In other words, the Constitution is the basis of all existing laws and the most fundamental sign of statehood.

After all, "each state, having chosen its own path of independence and development, will strengthen its most important goals and objectives, which will serve to ensure the well - being of the people, in its constitution-the Basic Law. Consequently, a country with a Constitution that is in tune with the will of its people, the good intentions of its language and language always goes forward, without ever deviating from the high milestones it has set".

When we look at the history of the Constitution of our country, first of all, "Timur's structures" appear before our eyes. In turn, the "Timur's structures" had the property of a constitutional document of a special form characteristic of

the civilisation of the countries of East and Asia, which, along with Sharia's laws, had a strong influence on the fate of the peoples of the Central Asian region.

Russian scientist with skirts D.Logofet studied "Timur's structures" and gave him a high assessment that the constitutional code that arose in Turkestan 500 years ago from Europe is, in other words, the Constitution of the Emir Timur Kingdom.

It has long been known which work is valuable in content-in essence in the idea, in practice it is very necessary, since then many copies have been copied and distributed. "Timur's tracts" were mainly considered an important guide for toju throne holders. That is why most of the rulers copied this work, kept it in their personal library and used it as an important guide in the political activities of the state.

The descendants of our great compatriot Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur ordered the skillful secretaries of the Shah World (1628-1657), the Khan of Kokand Muhammad Ali Khan (1821-1842) and the Emir of Bukhara Abdulahad Khan (1885-1910) and copied them for themselves from the "Timur's tracts" [29].

After the Republic of Uzbekistan declared its independence before the world community, we must separately state that, from the first Constitution of the Turkestan ASSR until the Constitution of the twelfth convocation adopted at the eleventh session of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 8, 1992, the Khorezm and Bukhara people have a history of more than 10

After the February Revolution of 1917, the network of Soviets of workers', soldiers' and peasant deputies in Russia grew rapidly. In may 1917, the I congress of peasant Soviets was held, and in June-workers and soldiers. The II Congress of Soviets of workers 'and soldiers' deputies, opened on October 25 of this year, announced that all power had passed into the hands of the Soviets in full. The III All-Russian Congress of Soviets, held in January 1918, adopted two acts of constitutional significance. This important document was the Declaration" on the rights of working and exploited people "and the decree" on federal institutions of the Russian Federation", in which the formation of the RSFSR was officially announced, and the first Constitution of the RSFSR was adopted at the V Congress of Soviets on July 10, 1918 . B. 244].

And before that, if we take a short look at the history of Russia's constitutions, the first Constitution corresponded to the era of Emperor Alexander I (1777-1825), according to his assignment, in 1819, the representative of the emperor N.N.Under the leadership of Novosilsev (1761-1838), a completely new draft law

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for the state "State Charter of the Russian Empire" was developed. However, this legislation was rejected by the emperor. The next movement for the Constitution was carried out by Alexander II (1818-1881), in 1881 the interior ministership count M.T.Loris-Melikov (1824-1888) presented to the emperor the "Loris-Melikov Constitution", which he developed. This project was usually to be approved by the emperor and placed in the Soviet of ministers mohokama. But, on this day, Alexander II was killed by the terrorists of the "people's will" ("Narodnaya Volya"). And on April 29, 1881, the "manifesto on the inviolability of autocracy" was developed by Alexander III (1845-1894), immediately ending the "Loris-Melikov Constitution". By 1905, the next emperor of Russia, Nicholas II (1868-1918), announced the "Supreme manifesto on improving state order". After the Bolsheviks came to power, one of the most basic problems that arose before them was the creation of a new form of statehood in the country. The development of a new management system in this regard has become one of the first tasks that need to be solved. In accordance with the existing revolutionary tradition and ideas about the essence of the new government, the Soviet republic was considered as the ideal of the political system. In this regard, since 1918, almost every year in the Soviet state, Soviet re-election campaigns were held, which were transformed into a broad form of attracting citizens of the country to state construction.

The sad thing was that a large part of the local population could not get acquainted with the main document that determined the state structure of the country, at least in a general way. The reason was that it was not published in local languages. In this document, the "self-determination" characteristic of the Soviets did not change the colonial status of the local population in Turkestan .

The second Constitution of the Turkestan ASSR was approved by the decree of the IX Congress of the Turkestan Assr Soviet on September 24, 1920, in which sections 1 and 2 were devoted to the "Declaration of Labor and expropriated people's rights" and "general provisions of the RSFSR Constitution". In Section 3, the rights of the Turkestan ASSR in the social and state structure and their relations with the RSFSR were indicated.

Both of the above constitutions, in their structure and essence of content, determined the exploitation of humanity as the main task of the young Soviet state and the destruction of the form of private ownership, as well as the establishment of the victory of socialism in all countries. The right to elect and be elected was granted to citizens who have reached the age of 18. Persons receiving income at the expense of mercenary Labor, people living at the

expense of non-labor income, merchants and intermediaries, representatives of religion, servants of the gendarmerie, employees of the police and Security Department were deprived of suffrage.

In addition, in its sections on "active and passive suffrage", almost no big difference is observed. Only Chapter 13 of the Constitution of 1918, dedicated to the "elections of Soviets and congresses", was divided into separate chapters in the Constitution of 1920, and the powers of deputies were extended from 3 to 6 months. The number of Deputies was increased from 30 to 50 for people living in villages, ovules and settlements. The number of Deputies who were shown to the congresses of the regional and uezd Soviets from the Soviets of cities and villages has changed dramatically.

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